

Late Medieval Brick Temples in the Hooghly district of West Bengal

Arabinda Singha Roy
Archaeology & Museology
Ranchi University

Accepted: November 2021 / Published online: December 2021

Abstract:

This article is about the brick built temples of the Hooghly district which were constructed during the late medieval period by local Zamindar or rich persons or renowned dacoits. Temples are classified based on their morphological features comparing with traditional architectural style. A short history about more or less all the temples complex is given. A light have been thrown on the decoration of the temple walls that came from different mythological tales, natures, and society. An attempt have also been made to know how these temple complexes became a part of the society and how economic activities are emerged centralizing the temple premises.

Keywords: Brick Temple, Terracotta, Ratna, Chala, Hooghly, Bangla

1. Introduction:

Hooghly is one of the districts in the state of West Bengal with four administrative divisions, i.e., Chinsura Sadar, Serampur, Chandannagar, and Arambagh. The district also spelt as Hoogli or Hugli derives its name from the town Hooghly situated on the river bank

Hugli about 40 km from the state head quarter Kolkata. The district has thousands of years of rich heritage as part of the Bhurshut Kingdom. In the middle of 18th century Bardhaman Raj occupied this region and proved their sovereignty over next few decades. This region was divided and ruled by landlords (Zamindar) in their respective area especially in the time of European colonization over this land. Most of the brick built temples were built on this land the middle of 16th century to 19th century when it was excluded direct ruled by any legitimate kingdoms (Mitra 1993). Cluster of temples is a main characteristic features in this district rather than sporadic found. Mainly, so far nine places have been marked with cluster of brick build temples in the different corner of the district, those are:

1. Singur (South Eastern part)
2. Baksha (South Central part of the district)
3. Ilchoba (Ilsoba) (North Eastern part of the District)
4. Somra (North Eastern Corner)
5. Guptipara (North Eastern Corner, not far from Somra)
6. Rajhati-Khanakul-Radhanagar (South Western Part of the District)
7. Antpur-Jangipara- Rajbalhat (Southern Part of the district)
8. Dasghara (North-central)
9. Bali-Dewanganj (Western part of the district)

All these clusters of brick built temples are built during the late medieval period, when this district was divided into several parts and ruled by different landlords. Most of the temples were patronized by local Zamindar or trader families, except a few ones, due to absent of any legitimate kingdom. Likewise, the Nandadulal Temple in Chandannagore established by Indranarayan Chowdhury who was the Diwan of the French Government in Chandannagore; the area around Singur was dominated by Gagan Sardar, a famous dacoit, and it is believed

the Dakat Kali temple was established by Gagan Sardar himself sometimes in 1850s; the temple complex at Satmandirtala of Singur were built in the early half of the 19th Century. The temples were established by Dwarkanath Wali, who was the zamindar of the region. The Wali family was established by Dwarkanath's father, Gopinath, who came to Bengal from the Punjab province who began as dacoits and after accumulating much wealth became Zamindar; the Dalan temple of Basumallik family was built in the mid of 19th century by Rajendranath who was a well-known physician during that period; more or less all the temple complexes in Baksha were constructed in the 18th Century by Bhairavcharan Mitra, who was the Diwan at Bardhaman; brick temples in around Itachuna were built in the middle of 19th century by local Maratha Zamindar Kundans family, presently known as Kundu family; whereas all the major temples in Ilchoba were built by local influential families, i.e., big siva temple complex by Indubhusan Bandopadhyay in the early 19th century, Siva temple by Srinath Das, well known 19th Century businessman of Calcutta, Thakurdalan was constructed by the Ghosh family, an affluent family of the village in mid-19th Century; the temples in Mondalai in Pandua were constructed by Kar family in the early 19th Century; same as the well-conserved temple complex at Sukhoria in Balagarh was constructed by the Bireswar Mitra Mustafi in 1813 on the land allotted to Anantaram Mitra Mustafi by Maharaja Tilakchand of Bardhaman sometimes in 18th Century, not only this temple but also built a fort with several temples and other religious structures. The main attraction is the *Chandimandap*, decorated with elaborate and intricate wood carving in Sripur, constructed in 1707 by the same family; Gopinath Jew and other temples at Krishnanagar market area in Khanakul were built by Abhirama Gopal known as Ram Das, a devotee of Lord Nityananda; on the other hand temples at Rajhati and Senhat were constructed by influential Chakrabarti and Ghosh family; temples in around the village Radhanagar in Khanakul were built by members of Raja Rammohan Roy family in the early 19th century; most of the temples at Bali- Deyanganj in Goghat were built by the family members of the local Zamindar Shiv babu; temples in Dasghara in Dhaniakhali were constructed by Roy or Dev Biswas families; temples in Janghipara Block including the

village of Antpur and Rajbalhat were built by the Rajas of Bhursut kingdom; and brick temples of Guptipara were built by the Zamindar of Sheoraphuli. Exceptional example is found in the case of Radhaballav temple, situated on the bank of river Ganga in Serampore was built by pundit Rudraram of Chatra in 1577 C.E. which later converted in a Church and known as Henry Martin's Pagoda (Crawford 1902; Mitra 1962).

However, the following list is made (Table 1A) with the major terracotta temples which are presently in the Hooghly district of West Bengal:

Temples of Hooghly District, West Bengal

Sl no	Name of the Temple	Location of the Temple
1	Dakat Kali Temple	Singur
2	Bon Bishalakshi Temple	Singur
3	Sat Mandir Tala	Singur
4	Jora Shiva Temple	Singur
5	Dalan Temple	Singur
6	Baro Shiva Temple	Baksha
7	Radhamadhav Temple	Baksha
8	Dalan Temple	Baksha
9	Shiva Temple	Khanyan
10	Dilapidated Temple	Ilchhoba
11	Temple Complex	Ilchhoba
12	Jora Shiva Temple	Ilchhoba
13	Dilapidated Shiva Temple	Ilchhoba
14	Siva Temple Complex	Ilchhoba
15	Temple Complex	Sukhoria (Somra)
16	Jagadhatri Temple	Sukhoria (Somra)

17	Durga Temple	Sripur
18	Radhaballav Temple (Henry Martin Pagoda)	Serampore
19	Radhaballav Temple	Serampore
20	Temple Complexes in Goswami Malipara	Sinhet/Goswa mi Malipara
21	Temples around Tribeni Ghat	Tribeni
22	Bajreshwar Temple	Rajhati
23	Visalaskhi Temple	Rajhati
24	Simhavahini Temple	Rajhati
25	Temple Complex	Rajhati
26	Gopinath Temple Complex	Krishnagar
27	Six Shiva Temple	Radhanagar
28	Dilapidated Deul Temple	Radhanagar
29	Jora Shiva Temple	Radhanagar
30	Chandi Mandap	Antpur
31	Radhagobinda Temple	Antpur
32	Temple Complex	Antpur
33	Temple Complex	Dasghara
34	Damodar Temple	Rajbalhat
35	Twin temples	Bansberia
36	Hangseshwari temple	Bansberia
37	Ananta Basudev Temple	Bansberia
38	Terracotta Temple Complex	Mahanad
39	Dilapidated Temple	Khanakul
40	Dolmancha	Khanakul
41	Brick Temple	Baichigram

42	Small Temple	Baichigram
43	Dilapidated Brick Temple	Baichigram
44	Dilapidated Brick Temples	Janghipara
45	Kalachand Temple	Bali-Dewangunj
46	Lakshmi-Janardhan Temple	Bali-Dewangunj
47	Dilaidated Rashmancha	Bali-Dewangunj
48	Chandi Mandap	Bali-Dewangunj
49	Rasmancha	Bali-Dewangunj
50	Damador Temple	Bali-Dewangunj
51	Dilapidated Rashmancha	Bali-Dewangunj
52	Dilapidated Temple	Bali-Dewangunj
53	Dilapidated At-chala	Bali-Dewangunj
54	Sarbamangala Temple	Bali-Dewangunj
55	Mangalchandi Temple	Bali-Dewangunj
56	Chaitanya Temple	Guptipara
57	Ramchandra Temple	Guptipara
58	Brindavanchandra Temple	Guptipara
59	Krishnachandra Temple	Guptipara

60	Nandadulal Temple	Chandannagar
61	Dalan Temple, Bazar Bari	Janai
62	Dalan Temple, Puratan Bari	Janai

63	Parvati Babau's Thakurdalan	Chanditala
64	Dwadoshi Siva Temple	Chanditala
65	Dalan Temple, Ghosh Family	Pandua

Table 1A; List of the Major Brick Temples in Hooghly district of West Bengal. Nature of the Temples:

Based on the nature and morphological features these sixty five temples of Hooghly district can be divided into several groups.

A. Temples with Enclosed *Garbhagriha*

B. *Rasmancha*

C. *Dalan* Temple

D. *Chandimandap*

2. A: Temples with Enclosed *Garbhagriha*

Temples which have a *garbhagriha* enclosed by four walls some time attached with *mandapa* through a narrow *antarala* can be placed in this classification. This type of temples further divided into several classes of traditional temple architectural styles (Saraswati 1963), these are:

i. *Char-chala*

ii. *At-chala*

iii. *Baro-chala*

iv. *Ek-Bangla*

v. *Eka-ratna*

vi. *Pancha-ratna*

vii. *Nava-ratna*

viii. *Trayadasa-ratna*

ix. *Panchavimsati-ratna*

x. *Rekha Deul*

xi. Dilapidated Temples

xii. Mixed style

Classification of these traditional styles, their origin and development have been analysis by numerous scholars (Dani 1961; Banerji 1968; Spooner 1916; McCutcheon 1972). Therefore, apart from origin, definition, and development an attempted has been made in this article to placed sixty five major temples into different traditional classes and architectural style would be analysis if necessary.

2. A. i. *Char-chala*:

Out of sixty five temples in this district only two temples, i.e., Bon Bishalakshi Temple at Singur (Figure 2. A. i.a) and Dilapidated Temple at Ilchhoba (Figure 2. A. i.b), are *char- chala* variety. Generally small and unpretentious, less decorated or completely plain except the frontal part. All these are on a square base as well as *char-chala* roof with a ridge along the top surmounts an enclosed lower structure. Sometimes a porch on three archways and sidechambers were built.

Figure 2. A. i. a: Bon Bishalakshi Temple at Singur Ilchhoba.

Figure 2. A. i. b: Dilapidated Temple at

2. A. ii. *At-chala*:

The commonest and most wide distributed temple style in the Hooghly district. Like the *char-chala* temple these type of temple is also stand on square base. An extra storey of four *chala* is built on the top of *char-chala* floor. The elongated *char-chala* with pillars both sides and entrances either end is also occasionally used for the *natamandapa* of *at-chala* temple is one of the main features in the *at-chata* temples in Hooghly district especially in Arambagh and Khanakul area. Total twenty such temples have been identified out of sixty five temples in this district (Table 2. A. ii).

Figure 2. A. ii. a: Baro Shiva Temple, Baksha.

Figure 2. A. ii. b: Radhaballav Temple (Henry Martin's Pagoda), Serampore.

Table Table 2. A. ii. List of the *At-chala* Temples, Hooghly District.

List of the At-chala Temples, Hooghly District.		
Sl no	Name of the temple	Location of the Temple
1	Dakat Kali Temple	Singur
2	Jora Shiva Temple	Singur
3	Sat Mandir Tala	Singur
4	Baro Shiva Temple	Baksha
5	Bajreshwar Temple	Rajhati
6	Brick Temple	Baichigram
7	Dilapidated Brick Temple	Baichigram
8	Dilapidated At-chala	Bali-Dewangunj
9	Damador Temple	Bali-Dewangunj
10	Dilapidated Temple	Khanakul
11	Dilapidated temple near Nagulpara	Khanakul
12	Jora Shiva Temple	Radhanagar
13	Six Shiva Temple	Radhanagar
14	Radhaballav Temple (Henry Martin Pagoda)	Serampore
15	Radhagobinda Temple	Antpur
16	Temple Complex	Antpur
17	Damodar Temple	Rajbalhat
18	Temple Complex	Ilchhoba
19	Temples around Tribeni Ghat	Tribeni
20	Dilapidated Brick Temples	Janghipara

Figure 2. A. ii. c: Six temples, Radhanagar, Khanakul.

2. A. iii. *Baro-chala*:

One of the rare Bengal traditional architectural style. A variety is found from Siva temple complex in Khanyan. Though McCutcheon (McCutcheon 1972, 40) reported another two temples of this variety in this district one from Ilchhoba and another from Senhat in Arambagh (now in Khanakul). In the time of survey the present author did not notice any such *baro-chala* temple in both of the places.

Figure 2. A. iii: *Baro-chala* temple in the Siva Temple Complex, Khanyan

2. A. iv. *Ek-Bangla*:

Comparatively rare architectural style. Two temples, i.e., Nandadulal temple in Chandannagar (Figure 2. A. iv. a), and Durga temple at Sripur (Figure 2. A. iv. b), of this style are found from this district. The Nandadulal temple has three arched doors with a few floral decoration and on the frontal side there is a staircase and a porch. The *ek-bangla* Durgamandap is brick built attached with a twenty four pillared *natamandapa*. Inner side of the brick structure is decorated by fine wood work. The roof is made of wooden frame presently cover by tin shed.

Figure 2. A. iv. a:

Nandadulal temple, Chandannagar.

Figure 2. A. iv. a:

Durga temple, Sripur.

2. A. v. Eka-ratna:

Easily distinguishable from which are consist of many towers. Four such temples, i.e., Ananta Basudev Temple at Bansberia (Figure 2. A. v), a small temple in the Baichigram, and two temples in the Gopinath Jew Temple complex in Krishnanagar, Khanakul, are found from this district. Though it is assumed that a broken temples, i.e., Lakshmi-Janardhan temple in Bali-Dewangunj was probably belonging to this architectural variety. The Ananta Basudev Temple at Bansberia have a square base with four entrance consisting with three arch well decorated doorways. The Lakshmi-Janardhan Temples in Bali-Dewangunj are broken.

Figure 2. A. v: Ananta Basudev Temple at Bansberia.

2. A vi. *Pancha-ratna*:

This type is also a common temple style in Bengal but this scenario have been changed in the case of Hooghly district where only five such pieces so far been reported. These are:

1. *Pancha-ratna* temple in Dasghara.
2. Two *Pancha-ratna* temples in the temple complex in Mahanad (Figure 2. A vi. a).
3. Damador temple, Bali-Dewangunj.
4. *Pancha-ratna* temple in Bansberia (Figure 2. A vi. b)
5. Two *Pancha-ratna* temples in the temple complex of Sukhoria.

Structures and ground plans of all these temples are almost same. Damador temple of Bali-Dewangunj is completely dilapidated.

Figure 2. A vi. a: *Pancha-ratna* Temples, Mahanad.
Bansberia.

Figure 2. A vi. b: *Pancha-ratna* Temple in
Bansberia.

5. A. vii. *Nava-ratna*:

A renowned design, the *nava-ratna* is basically a *pancha-ratna* with an extra story. Eight out of nine *ratnas* are equal in shape and size except the middle one which is large and more elaborate. Three temples of this variety have been reported which are:

1. A *nava-ratna* temple in the Gopinath temple complex, Krishnagar (Figure 5. A. vii. a).
2. A *nava-ratna* temple in Bansberia (Figure 5. A. vii. b).
3. Radhamadhav temple, Baksha.

Figure 5. A. vii. a: *Nava-ratna* temple, Krishnagar.

Figure 5. A. vii. b: *Nava-ratna* temple, Bansberia.

5. A. viii. *Trayadasa-ratna*:

This variety of temples are few in number. This type is formed by adding another storey of *mava-ratna*. Two temples, i.e., Hangseshwari temple in Bansberia (Figure 5. A. viii), and Mangalchandi temple in Bali-Dewangunj, are identified as *trayadasa-ratna* in the Hooghly district of West Bengal. Though in the the Mangalchandi temple in Bali-Dewangunj is completely ruined and presently no such traces of *trayadasa-ratna* as McCutchaion claimed (McCutchaion 1972, 55).

Figure 5. A. viii: Hangseshwari temple, Bansberia.

JHAM

5. A. ix. *Panchavimsati-ratna*:

A rare variety of temple style. Only one temple, i.e., Anandamayee temple in Sukhoria (Figure 5. A. ix), is identified with this style. Three-storied type temple arrange its turrets in groups of three at each corner of the first storey, two at the each corner in the second, and one at each corner at the third storey surmounted by the topmost tower. Total thirteen temples are there in this temple complex, out of which ten temples are *at-chala* types, two are of *pancha-ratna*, and the main temple is of *Panchavimsati-ratna*.

Figure 5. A. ix: Anandamayee temple complex, Sukhoria (Somra).

5. A. x. Rekha Deul:

Prominent style of the districts to the bordering on Odisha and Bihar. A temple with this variety has been reported from Radhanagar in Khanakul (Figure 5. A. x). So such name is given to the temple. It is deserted and dilapidated partially. The temple has *triratha* projection with a smooth curvilinear *sikhara* decorated by different iconographical features with in niches. Most of the images are of siva. A plaque is in front of the temple mentioned a date, i.e., 1750 *saka* era, and 1235 Bengali era, when it was built probably by the members of the Raja Rammahon Roy's family.

Figure 5. A. x: Rekha Deul, Radhanagar, Khanakul.

5. A. xi. Dilapidated Temples:

Many of the temples noted in this district are in dilapidated condition due to years of negligence. But this category is made with unrecognizable temple styles due to completely broken. Only two temples are placed in this category which are:

1. Dilapidated siva temple at Ilchhoba (Figure 5. A. xi. a) and,
2. Ruined brick temple beside the road side at Bali-Dewangunj (Figure 5. A. xi. b).

Figure 5. A. xi. a: Dilapidated Temple, Ilchhoba. Figure 5. A. xi. b: Dilapidated temple, Bali-Dewangunj.

5. A. xii. Mixed style:

A few example have come out which cannot be placed within a certain traditional style. Those are result of mixture of two traditional styles. Sometimes those temples are also placed in this category which are situated in a complex but built out with different styles. The

following are the temples of different styles.

1. Simhavahini Temple at Rajhati and Brick Temple at Baichigram (Figure 5. A. xii. 1):

An *at-chala* temple attached with a *char-chala* porch (*bhogamandapa*).

2. Gopinath Temple Complex at Krishnagar, Khanakul:

Three big temples are in this complex with a *rasmancha*. One is *pancha-ratna* variety, another one came out with *eka-ratna* style with a small *sikhara* in the front of the ridge, and the last one is very interesting which is admixture of *char-chala* and *eka-ratna* style (Figure 5. A. xii. 2).

3. Kalachand Temple at Bali-Dewangunj (Figure 5. A. xii. 3):

The temple is situated behind the *Siva kuthi* in Bali-Dewangunj. It is *eka-ratna* variety with a hexagonal base, but the *ratna* is placed on high two storeyed arched platform. If these arches are consider as *chala* then the temple is an admixture of twelve *chala* and *eka-ratna*. A broken *natamandapa* is found in front of the temple.

4. Radhagobinda Temple at Antpur (Figure 5. A. xii. 4):

A beautifully decorated *at-chala* temple attached with a porch of *ek-bangla* style.

5. Sarbamangala Temple at Bali-Dewangunj (Figure 5. A. xii. 5):

A well decorated temple among the temples of Bali-Dewangunj. This is a result of the admixture of *jor-bangla* and *nava-ratna* style.

6. Visalaskhi Temple at Rajhati (Figure 5. A. xii. 6):

The main temple is *at-chala* variety with a square base and light decorated frontal wall. Interestingly, an *ek-bangla* style *natamandapa* is made in front of the main temple.

7. Temple Complex at Rajhati (Figure 5. A. xii. 7):

Two different style of temple is found in a complex along with a *pancharatna Rasmancha*. Among two of the main temples, one is made with *at-chala* style and another one is *rekha deul* variety. A pillared *natamandapa* is seen in front of the *at-chala* temple with a shed of tin.

8. Temple Complex at Ilchhoba (Figure 5. A. xii. 8):

Three temples are there in the complex. One is octagonal base. Is has eight gates and nine *sikharas*, i.e., *nava-ratna* variety. Other two temples in this complex are *at-chala* variety.

Figure 5. A. xii.1: Brick Temple, Baichigram. Figure 5.A.xii. 3: Kalachand Temple, Bali-Dewangunj. Figure 5.A. xii.4: Radhagobinda Temple at Antpur

Figure 5.A.xii.2: *Eka-Ratna* on *char-chala* variety, Gopinath Temple complex, Krishnagar.

Figure 5. A. xii. 5: Sarbamangala Temple, Bali-Dewangunj

Figure 5. A. xii. 8: Temple Complex at Ilchhoba Figure 5. A. xii. 6: Visalaskhi Temple at Rajhati

Figure 5. A. xii. 7: Temple Complex at Rajhati.

2. B. Rasmancha:

These temples were built for performing the *rasa* festival. More or less in every temple complex a *rasmancha* is found. In total the following *rasmanchos* are noted from the different villages of Hooghly districts:

1. Dilapidate Rasmancha at Bali-Dewangunj.
2. Hexagonal Rasmancha at Bali-Dewangunj.
3. Rasmancha near Radhanagar, Khanakul (*Pancha-ratna*) (Figure 2. B.1).
4. Hexagonal dilapidated Rasmancha at Bali-Dewangunj (Figure 2. B. 2).
5. Rasmancha at Dasghara (Octagonal with *nine ratnas*).
6. Rasmancha at Baichigram (*eka-ratna*).
7. Rasmancha at Atnpur (*Pancha-ratna*).
8. Rasmancha at Sripur (Hexagonal with *Sapta-ratna*).
9. Rasmancha at Krishnanagar, Khanakul (*at-chala*).
10. Rajmancha at Rajhati (*pancha-ratna*).

JHAM

Figure 2.B.1: Rasmancha near Radhanagar, Khanakul.

Figure 2.B.2: Dilapidated Rasmancha, Bali-Dewangunj

2. D. Dalan Temple

Generally built within the premise of house or with the Zamindar bari by any Zamindar or influential rich persons to worship their deity. This type of architectural style consisting of pillared hall with multi arched doorways. Nine such temples are found with the building complex from this district. These are:

1. **Dalan temple at Baksha** (Within the house of the Mitra family, constructed in the 18th Century by Bhairavcharan Mitra)
2. **Dalan Temple, Apurbapur, Singur** (Belongs to the Basumallik family, constructed in mid-19th Century by Rajendranath Basumallik and Surendranath Basumallik)
3. **Dalan Temple, Bajar Bari, Janai** (Within the house of Mukherjee family, Constructed in early 19th Century by Bhawanicharan and Bholanath Mukherjee)
4. **Dalan Temple, Paratan Bari, Janai** (Belongs to the Mukherjee family, was constructed by Bhawanicharan Mukherjee in late 18th Century)

5. **Parvati Babu's Thakurdalan, Chanditala** (Within the house of Mukherjee family, completed by his son Parvati Charan Mukherjee in mid-19th Century)
6. **Dalan Temple, Kaliprasad Mukhopadhyay Bari** (Within the Maharaja Kaliprasad Mukhopadhyay house, constructed by Maharaja Kaliprasad Mukhopadhyay in 1234 Bengali era)
7. **Dalan Temple, Kundu Bari, Khanyan** (Within the house of Kundu family, Constructed in mid-19th Century by the descendants of Safally Narayan Kundu) (Figure 2.D. 2)
8. **Datan Temple, Dasghara** (not known properly)
9. **Dalan Temple, Tribeni** (Within the house of Pandit Jagannath Tarkapanchanan constructed by him in between 1730-1750) (Figure 2 .D. 1).

Figure 2.D.1: *Dalan Temple, Tribeni*

Figure 2.D.2: *Dalan Temple, Kundu Bari, Khanyan*

2. E. *Chandimandap*:

Specially made for the goddess *Chandi*. *Chadimandap* always came out with a unique architecture generally *ek-bangla* variety of traditional temple style. Two such temples are

found from the Hooghly district. One is from Sripur which is already described in *ek-bangla* variety of temple (Ref 2. A. iv). Such as the finest wooden work yet to be found from the district of west Bengal. The other one is noted at Antpur (Figure 2. E). The temple is *ek-bangla* variety covered with a thatch roof.

Figure 2. E: *Chandimandap*, Antpur.

JHAM

3. Temple Decoration:

Generally bricks temples are decorated with terracotta plaques in different themes it may be taken from religious text or it could be from society or nature. More or less major important brick temples of Hooghly district have been presented with their architectural styles. Most of them are also ornamented but not such a way which have been noticed in the temples of Birbhum and Bankura district. A good number of temples in this district is of *at-chala* types merely one frontal outer wall of this style of temples is found with decoration, rest of the part remain undecorated. Temples are numerous in count but large temples with marvellous decoration are a few. However, decorated panels on the surfaces can be separated into three segments on the ground of the sources of the themes.

Figure 3.1: Floral decorated entrance panel, Baichigram

Figure 3.3: Entrance Panel, Lakshmi-

Temple, Bal-Dewangunj.

First of all religious themes. Most of the panels which are seen in the entrance above the arch doorways generally taken from religious texts, except a few exceptions where this central panes are also decorated with beautiful floral decoration (Figure 3. 1). Different tales of Ramayana are depicted throughout these panels basically the war fought between Rama

and Ravana (Figure 3. 2). Another story also taken for decorated the central panels that is from the Vaishnava faith of love and intimation (Figure 3.3). On both the sides' panels beside the entrance are found depiction of different forms of Vishnu or individual deities (Figure 3.4). On the top of the entrance panels individual forms of deities are found along with the forms of the deity whom the temple is dedicated (Figure 3.5). Except these, different forms

Figure 3.5: Depiction different forms of goddess Kali, Anandamayee temple, Sukhoria.

of different deities can be seen on the pillars or on the side panels sometimes. It is said that effect of bhakti movement and influence of Vaishnavism most of the terracotta temples were built. In some aspect this view found a relevance ground when a *rashmancha* is seen in a temple complex. This view is more prominent in the case of the group of temples at Krishnanagar in Khanakul which was built by Abhiram Gopla a close of Nityananda prabhu

and also a devoted Vaishnava. Depiction of *Rashmandala* (Figure 3.5) in the surface of the temples supports this view strongly.

Fig.3.6: Warfare, Dasghara. Fig. 3.7: European vessel, Baichigram.

Fig.3.4: Damador temple, Balidewangunj.

Figure 3.2: Depiction of war between Rama and Ravana, Damador temple, Rajbalhat.

Social scenes are more commonly found on the surfaces of the outer walls. Generally base of the temple is decorated with social themes. Social themes were taken from circumstantial social environments. A major parts of the social these comes from the war which was probably often phenomenon on that time in this district of peripheral regions (Figure 3. 6). Depiction of European communities on the side panels reflects a new era of socialism as well as process of colonization (Figure 3. 7). Different type of activities of the society are also depicted throughout the walls of the temples like, dance, drama, playing musical instruments, weaving cloths (Figure 3.7), smoking hookah (Figure 3.8), etc. Royal coronation or activities of kings and queens can also be taken for temple decoration. Erotic scenes are also secure their place in the decoration of temples (Figure 3.9).

Figure 3.7: Dasghara.

Figure 3.8: Baichigram.

Figure 3.9: Dasghara.

Figure 3.5: Rashmadala, Temple complex, Mahanad.

4. General Observation:

The following observations can be drawn after analysis the temples, its style, and illustration on the surface:

1. First of all location of the Hooghly district is very crucial. River like Damador, Dwarkeswar, and Ganga drain through this district. In every year new alluvium soil is formed due to floor. The soil of these river catchment areas are fertile, levigated and handy. So, raw materials for constructing temple are locally available. It is seen that there is pond beside every terracotta temple which were used for secret purpose. These ponds were formed due to drug out muds for making brick and terracotta panels. Therefore, it can be assuming that availability of raw materials probably responsible for constructing numerous brick temples in this district.

II. The earliest temple in this district is found to be constructed on the bank of river Ganga in Serampore by pundit Rudraram of Chatra in 1577 C.E., the process of construction of temples were continued up to the middle of the 19th century. Temples were constructed within the zamindar houses or nearby to worship by the members of the royal families and sometimes for their tenants. A few temples are seen constructed far from the zamindar or royal houses by any devotee or rich or influential person.

III. We have already discuss about the nine clusters of temple and their style. It can be seen that a particular style flourished in a particular region. The cluster of temples of Atnpur, Rajbalhat and Jangipara were made by the influence of *at-chala* variety of traditional temple style. Same influence can be seen of the temples of Guptipara. On the other hand different style of temples can be seen in Rajhati, Krishnangar, and Radhanagar. Along with *chala* temples, *deul*, *eka-ratna*, *pancha-ratna*, and composite style like *ratna on chala* or *chalata* with *bangla* can be seen stand besides all together. Bali- Dewangunj gave us versatile temples style in a certain and limited area. Most of the temple are ruins and dilapidated condition but it must be said that among all the clusters this complex gave us well-decorated and outstanding works of terracotta art.

IV. It is beyond doubt that building a temple is a luxurious and prestigious work it might require lot of financial support. On that cause patronizing the temples were generally made by Rajas, Zamindar, or rich persons. In the early mediaeval period Hooghly district was divided by Zamindars who were patronized these terracotta temples, but they had also a limited resources. Absent of the legitimate kingdom may cause not to developed any such huge and marvellous temple complex in this district.

V. These temples are not important only for religious purpose but also social and economic aspect. Even today peoples are gathering in these temples for their religious believe. Markets are developed centralizing these temples. Economy of a region sometimes depends on these temples as example we can consider the Gopinath jew temple at Krishnanagar in Khanakul. Day to day life of many persons are entirely depend on this temple to serving the *ghog*

or supplying the *puja* materials. It will not be wrong to say that the nearby Krishnanagar marked was once originated depending on this temple complex.

However, after all by the patronizing of Zamindar and rich persons this district have more than sixty five terracotta temples which were constructed in the late medieval period using local materials by the influence of Vaishnavism and still standing indulging religion, economic and social life of the local people.

References

- Banerji, Adris.(1968). *Temples of Tripura*. Varanasi: Prithivi Prakashan.
- Crawford, Dirom Gray.(1902). *A Brief History of Hooghly District*. Calcutta: Bengal Secretariat Press.
- Dani, A.H.(1961). *Muslim Architecture in Bengal*. Dacca: Asiatic Society of Pakistan.
- McCutchion, David J.(1972). *Late Mediaeval Temples of Bengal*. Calcutta: The Asiatic Society.
- Mitra, Debala.(1993). *Hooghly Jelar Purakriti*. Calcutta: West Bengal State Archaeology.
- Mitra, Sudhir Kumar.(1962). *Hooghly Jelar Itihash o Bangasamaj*. Calcuta: Mondal Book House.
- Spooner, D.B.(1916). "Temples Types in Trihut." *Journal of the Bihar and Orissa Research Society*, pp. 119-134.